

1 System-based reliability analysis of stainless steel frames subjected to gravity and wind loads

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7 **ABSTRACT**

8 In the process of developing the next generation of design standards for steel structures, most relevant
9 international structural codes including AISC 360, AISC 370, AS/NZS 4100 and Eurocode 3 already
10 incorporate preliminary versions of system-based *design-by-analysis* approaches that allow a direct
11 evaluation of the strength of steel and stainless steel structures from advanced numerical simulations. As
12 a result, recent research works have focused on building rigorous structural reliability frameworks to
13 investigate acceptable target reliability indices for structural systems and to develop new design methods
14 in conjunction with adequate system safety factors and system resistance factors. Although design
15 recommendations exist for the direct design of hot-rolled and cold-formed steel structures based on
16 advanced finite element analysis, the extension of the method to other materials such as stainless steel is
17 under development. This paper is part of a research effort to build a reliability framework for stainless
18 steel structures subject to different load combinations and presents the results of system reliability
19 calibrations carried out on six stainless steel portal frames subjected to combined gravity and wind loads.
20 The study covers the most common stainless steel families and three international design frameworks (i.e.,
21 Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks). From the reliability calibrations derived, suitable system
22 safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_S are proposed for the direct design of stainless steel
23 frames under combined gravity and wind loads using advanced numerical simulations.

24 **KEYWORDS**

25 advanced analysis; probability-based design; reliability calibrations; stainless steel structures; structural
26 reliability; wind loads

27 HIGHLIGHTS

- 28 • Application of the system-based direct design method to stainless steel frames subjected to
29 combined gravity and wind loads is presented.
- 30 • Six baseline cold-formed stainless steel frames are investigated, including the three main stainless
31 steel families.
- 32 • System reliability calibrations are presented for the Eurocode, US and Australian design
33 frameworks, covering different wind-to-dead load ratios.
- 34 • System safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_S are proposed for the target reliability
35 indices typically adopted in national design frameworks.

36 1. INTRODUCTION

37 As a consequence of the rapid advances in design software and the growth of computational features of
38 desktop computers over the last decade, the behaviour and failure of complex structural systems can be
39 accurately predicted. In response to these advances, current research efforts are focused on the
40 development of direct *design-by-analysis* approaches, in which the analysis and design are carried out
41 simultaneously (*single-step* process) by accounting for all geometric and material nonlinearities in the
42 analysis and without the use of analytical design expressions. Direct design approaches can be applied
43 to members (e.g., beam-columns), parts of structures (e.g., a module of a box-girder comprising the
44 deck of a bridge) or systems (e.g., full frames). In this process, most relevant design codes for steel and
45 stainless steel structures in the Australian, US and Eurocode frameworks (AS/NZS 4100 [1], AISC 360-
46 16 [2], AISC 370-21 [3], prEN 1993-1-14 [4]) already incorporate preliminary versions of direct design
47 methods, although current design provisions are still primarily based on the conventional *two-step*
48 approaches [1-3,5-8]. In the *two-step* limit state approach, designers are required to determine internal
49 actions from a usually elastic structural analysis and to subsequently check the ultimate capacity of the
50 different members and connections comprising the structural system. Alternatively, when designing (or
51 verifying) with direct methods the strength of a member or a structure can be directly evaluated from
52 advanced simulations without requiring further checks; when applied to systems, the load redistribution
53 capacity, redundancy and robustness of the structures can be fully exploited, ensuring a more uniform

54 reliability across different structural systems and potentially leading to lighter and more economical
 55 designs [9].

56 In the traditional *two-step* approach, the random variations of design parameters are dealt with
 57 nominal or characteristic values and the use of the partial coefficients, and the capacity of structures is
 58 generally limited to the resistance of individual members or connections, which are evaluated from
 59 time-consuming and often complex design expressions. Conversely, direct design procedures are
 60 simple, as shown in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 for the Eurocode and the US/Australian design frameworks,
 61 respectively, where R_k (or R_n) is the characteristic (or nominal) resistance of the system, γ_i is the load
 62 magnification factor, Q_{ki} (or Q_{ni}) denotes the characteristic (or nominal) structural loads, and $\gamma_{M,s}$ (or
 63 ϕ_s) is the partial safety factor (or resistance factor) of the system.

$$\frac{R_k}{\gamma_{M,s}} \geq \sum \gamma_i Q_{ki} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\phi_s R_n \geq \sum \gamma_i Q_{ni} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

64 When nonlinear structural analyses are carried out, design loads are generally applied proportionally
 65 and incrementally by using a load scale factor λ . The ultimate load scale factor λ_u (when the frame is
 66 at the state of incipient collapse) is referred to as the resistance of the frame. In such cases, Eq. 1 and
 67 Eq. 2 can be rewritten as Eq. 3 and Eq. 4, respectively. Obviously, the ultimate load scale factor
 68 corresponds to a particular load pattern, and consequently, the statistics of λ_u (and the corresponding
 69 $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s factors) may depend on the loading pattern. The present study assumes some representative
 70 loading patterns and different loading scenarios for stainless portal frames, and it is expected that these
 71 will cover the typical design situations.

$$\lambda_u \geq \gamma_{M,s} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\lambda_u \geq \frac{1}{\phi_s} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

73 Despite including direct design approaches, current design standards [1-4] do not provide system-based
 74 safety factors (or resistance factors). Rather, they require a comparable or higher level of reliability than
 75 that achieved for existing member-based provisions without stating how this may be demonstrated.
 76 Hence, it is necessary to determine suitable system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ or system resistance factors ϕ_s
 77

78 from rigorous structural reliability considerations for different structural types and materials to be
79 adopted in system-based direct design approaches. Based on recent research works over the last years,
80 design recommendations have been proposed for the design of hot-rolled steel frames [9-12], cold-
81 formed steel frames [13,14], steel storage rack frames [15] and steel scaffolds [16] using system-based
82 direct design approaches. However, the extension of the recommendations to different materials such
83 as stainless steel structures requires independent reliability calibrations due to the noticeable nonlinear
84 stress-strain response and significant strain-hardening properties exhibited by this material [17-19]. This
85 is being addressed in the NewGeneSS project [20]. To date, system safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system
86 resistance factors ϕ_S have been derived for stainless steel frames under gravity loads [21], based on the
87 statistical characterization of the different random variables affecting the strength of stainless steel
88 structures reported in [22].

89 This paper presents the extension of the system-based direct design approach to stainless steel cold-
90 formed portal frames subjected to combined gravity and wind loads through the calibration of suitable
91 system safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and resistance factors ϕ_S . A brief description of the baseline frames and the
92 developed Finite Element models is given in Section 2, while the load pattern adopted and the failure
93 modes of the frames are described in Section 3. Section 4 builds the full reliability analysis framework
94 for stainless steel frames, including the probabilistic models considered for the different random
95 variables and the methodology adopted for the calibration of system reliabilities. Finally, Section 5
96 presents and compares the results of the reliability calibrations for the different design frameworks
97 investigated, proposes suitable system safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and resistance factors ϕ_S for the Eurocode,
98 US and Australian frameworks, compares the baseline frames with those designed using the traditional
99 two-step approach and provides recommendations for specification committees.

100 **2. FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING**

101 2.1. DESCRIPTION OF BASELINE FRAMES

102 The system-based reliability calibrations presented in this paper are based on the results of six single-
103 storey, single-bay stainless steel portal frames of the type shown in Figure 1, featuring the typical
104 austenitic stainless steel grade EN 1.4301 (ASTM 304) for Frames 1 and 2, the common EN 1.4462

105 (ASTM 2205) duplex stainless steel grade for Frames 3 and 4, and the basic ferritic grade EN 1.4003
106 (ASTM UNS S40977) for Frames 5 and 6. These six baseline frames are identical to those adopted in
107 [21] for the reliability analysis of stainless steel frames under gravity loads, with the overall frame
108 geometries (span length s , heights at the eaves H_1 and at the roof ridge H_2) summarized in Table 1. All
109 frames comprised cold-formed rectangular hollow section (RHS) members, with uniform section
110 geometries for all rafters and columns. Frames 1, 3 and 5 featured the compact $150 \times 100 \times 4$ cross-section
111 and Frames 2, 4 and 6 were made from the slender $250 \times 150 \times 4$ cross-section, where the $H \times B \times t$ notation
112 indicates the cross-section height H , width B and thickness t . Note that Frames 1, 3 and 5 had the same
113 overall and cross-sectional dimensions but different materials, which allowed evaluating the effect of
114 the stainless steel family on the derived system reliabilities.

115 Stainless steel alloys exhibit a pronounced nonlinear stress-strain response with significant strain-
116 hardening, which is one of their most characteristic features together with their inherent corrosion
117 resistance [17,18]. To describe both material nonlinearity and strain-hardening, the two-stage model
118 proposed in [23,24] and adopted in the current international design standards for stainless steel
119 structures was used [3,4,7,25], with the basic material parameters specified in the relevant material
120 standards [3,7,25,26]. Since the cross-sections analysed were cold-formed, the increase in resistance
121 due to the significant plastic deformations occurring during the manufacturing process were considered
122 through the enhanced yield stress values predicted from the model proposed in [27]. The nominal stress-
123 strain curves for the different stainless steel alloys corresponding to the three design frameworks are
124 shown in Figure 2.

125 The stiffened welded knee connections suitable for rigid portal frames defined in [28] were adopted
126 for the joints of the cold-formed RHS frames, since these connections provide sufficient rotation
127 capacity for plastic hinges to develop. According to the discussion presented in [21], the moment-
128 rotation curve of these connections can be reasonably represented by a bi-linear model defined through
129 two stiffness parameters K_1 , K_2 and two moment capacities M_1 and M_2 . The nominal parameters
130 defining the behaviour of the connections at the eaves, apexes and column bases are identical to those
131 adopted in [21] except for the base connections in Frames 2, 4 and 6, which featured pin-ended base
132 support conditions under gravity loads only, and are reported in Table 1. Note that this study does not

133 consider joint failure; it assumes that the joints possess sufficient strength and ductility for their failure
134 (e.g., brittle failure) not to occur prior to reaching the ultimate limit states of the frames. This assumption
135 is, however, only valid for the calibration of system safety and resistance factors carried out in this
136 paper. In practical design, and while the existing DDM recommendations do not feature joint failure,
137 engineers should verify that the connections do not fail under the predicted frame capacity using current
138 design specifications, and demonstrate that they possess sufficient strength and ductility for the frame
139 ultimate limit states to be reached.

140 2.2. DESCRIPTION OF FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

141 System strengths of cold-formed stainless steel frames were estimated from advanced finite element
142 simulations using the general-purpose software ABAQUS [29]. The FE model used to simulate the
143 behaviour of stainless steel frames under combined gravity and wind loads was identical to that used in
144 [21] for gravity load cases, to which only small changes were made to introduce the wind loads. The
145 full details of the finite element models are described and discussed in [21] and only the key aspects are
146 summarized in this Section. The frames were modelled using S4R shell elements [21,30-32], with a
147 mesh size of approximately 25 mm × 25 mm as per the mesh convergence study reported in [21]. The
148 finite element models developed included local, member out-of-straightness and frame out-of-
149 plumbness initial geometric imperfections, with appropriate shapes and amplitudes: while the
150 requirements in [1-4,6,33] were followed for the imperfections in nominal frames, the values
151 determined from the statistical distributions discussed in Section 4.1 were adopted for the structural
152 analysis models. The full discussion on the initial imperfections considered by the different design
153 frameworks can be found in [21]. These imperfections were input in the FE models following different
154 strategies: while local and member imperfections were introduced from prior linear buckling analyses,
155 global imperfections were directly defined by offsetting the position of the nodes.

156 This study assumed bending residual stresses following the model proposed in [34] for cold-formed
157 stainless steel rectangular hollow sections, which were introduced as initial stresses in the FE models,
158 and membrane residual stresses were neglected. Likewise, material properties were assigned to the
159 different models through user-defined true stress vs true plastic strain relationships, assuming a von
160 Mises yield surface with isotropic hardening [35] and the associated flow rule available in ABAQUS

161 [29]. The frame models comprised four independent columns and rafters, which were connected to each
162 other through the combination of kinematic couplings, reference points and *HINGE*, *BEAM* and
163 *UJOINT* connector elements described in [21], to which user-defined bi-linear moment-rotation curves
164 were specified. To limit the response of the frames to the in-plane behaviour, the out-of-plane
165 displacements of the nodes defining the apex and eaves joint points, and the mid-height sections of the
166 columns and the mid-length sections of the rafters were restrained.

167 The ultimate frame loads were determined from static pushover analyses in which dead loads were
168 first applied at the upper faces of the rafters as *TRVEC* surface traction loads, followed by the wind
169 loading pattern shown in Figure 1 until the collapse of the frames was reached. Wind loads were
170 introduced as *PRESSURE* loads using the appropriate magnitude and sign in each column and rafter.
171 While the geometrically and materially nonlinear analyses corresponding to the dead loading
172 increments were performed using the Static General method, the Static Riks method was adopted for
173 the analysis of wind loading increments [29].

174 2.3. VALIDATION OF FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

175 The validation of the developed finite element models was carried out by comparing the experimental
176 results of the stainless steel frame tests reported in [32,36] with the corresponding simulation results
177 obtained from the FE model described in Section 2.2. The experimental specimens corresponded to four
178 single-span, single-storey cold-formed RHS austenitic stainless steel frames featuring compact and
179 slender sections, and were subjected to vertical and horizontal loading. The FE models used in the
180 validation were built as discussed in the previous Section, but included some specific features measured
181 from the experimental specimens and reported in [32,36], including loading sequence and the position
182 of the loads, material properties (obtained from tensile coupon tests), the rotational stiffness values at
183 the connections (estimated from experimental results at the base and eaves joints), and initial
184 imperfection amplitudes (measured from the specimens). Details of the model validation, the results in
185 terms of numerical-to-experimental load ratios and displacement ratios, and the comparison between
186 experimental and numerical load-displacement curves can be found in [21], which indicated that the
187 developed FE models were capable of accurately replicating the behaviour of the frames under
188 combined vertical and horizontal loading. It should be noted that although the actual properties

189 measured from the specimens were adopted in the simulations reproducing the tests for the validation
190 of the FE model, random properties based on the stochastic models discussed in Section 4.1 were
191 assumed for the simulations considered in reliability calibrations.

192 3. STAINLESS STEEL FRAMES UNDER GRAVITY AND WIND LOADS

193 3.1. GRAVITY AND WIND LOADING

194 The reliability calibrations for stainless steel frames subjected to wind loads were based on a loading
195 pattern that combines both gravity and wind loads, as shown in Figure 1. The ultimate limit states of
196 the frames were determined from static pushover analyses in which dead loads G_k or D_n were firstly
197 applied to the rafters in full, followed by the incremental application of wind loading until the lateral
198 resistance of the frames was reached (i.e., the frame was “pushed” over). To investigate the effect of
199 the wind-to-dead load ratio in reliability calibrations, three different values of design (nominal) dead
200 loads G_k (or D_n) were considered for each frame, namely the GW1, GW2 and GW3 load scenarios,
201 representing relatively light, medium and heavy wind loads, as reported in Table 1.

202 Nominal wind load patterns and magnitudes are prescribed in the different wind loading standards
203 for the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks, prEN 1991-1-4 [37], ASCE 7-16 [38] and
204 AS/NZS 1170.2 [39], respectively. The characteristic value of the wind load for the Eurocode
205 framework is given by Eq. 5, in which c_e is the exposure factor accounting for the effect of height and
206 terrain roughness, c_p is the pressure coefficient, c_s is the size factor, c_d is the dynamic amplification
207 factor and q_{ref} is the peak velocity pressure, which is dependent on the square of the wind speed.

$$W_k = c_e \cdot c_p \cdot c_s \cdot c_d \cdot q_{ref} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

208 Alternatively, the general form of the wind load acting on a structure according to the ASCE 7-16 [38]
209 Specification is given in Eq. 6, where C is a constant, G is the gust factor, C_p is the pressure coefficient,
210 K_z is the exposure factor, K_d is the directionality coefficient and V_{max} is the wind speed. The wind load
211 corresponding to the Australian framework given in AS/NZS 1170.2 [39] can be generally written as
212 per in Eq. 7, in which c is a constant, C_{fig} and C_{dyn} are the aerodynamic shape factor and the dynamic
213 response factor, respectively, and $V_{des,\theta}$ is the orthogonal design wind speed, which depends on the
214 wind speed, the terrain, the shielding and the topography.
215

$$W = C \cdot G \cdot C_p \cdot K_z \cdot K_d \cdot V_{\max}^2 \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$W = c \cdot C_{\text{fig}} \cdot C_{\text{dyn}} \cdot V_{\text{des},\theta}^2 \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

216
217 From these wind load models, it is evident that, despite featuring several modifying coefficients, the three
218 models include a part that is a function of the square of the wind speed and different time-invariant factors
219 related to the roughness, exposure and dynamic effects that depend on the characteristics of the site and
220 the interaction between the structure and the wind. The three wind load models prescribed in the different
221 specifications present different definitions for the wind field characteristics and the magnitudes of the
222 nominal wind loads depend on several factors, the most relevant of which are the averaging times for basic
223 wind velocity (ASCE 7-16 [38] and AS/NZS 1170.2 [39] define the basic wind speed as 3-s gust speed
224 whereas prEN 1991-1-4 [37] defines it as the 10-min mean wind speed), the wind velocity profiles
225 (AS/NZS 1170.2 and prEN 1991-1-4 use logarithmic laws, whereas ASCE 7 uses a power law) and the
226 internal and external pressure coefficients (which determine the wind loading patterns and essentially
227 depend on the geometry of the frame – pitch angle, number of openings – and the direction of the wind),
228 inevitably presenting some variability in the final wind loads. A study comparing international wind load
229 specifications found that, although significant discrepancies exist for the intermediate parameters, the
230 different models result in reasonably consistent overall loads when the basic wind velocity is modified to
231 match the velocity pressure and the same force/pressure coefficients are assumed [40].

232 When defining the wind loading pattern adopted in this study, the provisions and pressure
233 coefficients prescribed in prEN 1991-1-4 [37] were considered. Wind pressures on wall and roof
234 elements were determined for the overall frame geometries given in Table 1 and resulted in the average
235 external wind pressure distribution shown in Figure 1, which is similar to the pattern adopted in a recent
236 reliability study on steel frames carried out in the Eurocode framework [41]. Although it is based on
237 prEN 1991-1-4 [37] provisions, this study assumed that the wind loading pattern is still applicable to
238 the analysis of the US and Australian design frameworks since the differences in design wind loads are
239 fundamentally governed by the wind load magnitudes rather than by the loading patterns resulting from
240 particular pressure coefficients. Note that this paper assumes ordinary (synoptic) winds, without
241 considering coastal areas subjected to tropical cyclones or hurricane-prone regions.

242 3.2. FAILURE MODES OF BASELINE FRAMES

243 This Section describes the failure modes observed for the six baseline nominal frames under the dead
244 and wind loading pattern shown in Figure 1. Nominal models were built using the FE model described
245 in Section 2.2, the parameters reported in Table 1 and the nominal material properties specified in
246 [3,7,25,26]. The failure modes observed for each frame in the three design frameworks investigated
247 were essentially the same, although the values of the predicted ultimate failure wind loads were found
248 to be slightly different, as discussed in Section 5.1.

249 Frames 1, 3 and 5 had relatively low heights and spans, and each frame corresponded to one of the
250 three stainless steel families investigated, austenitic, duplex and ferritic stainless steel alloys,
251 respectively. At the ultimate limit state, these frames exhibited considerable lateral drifts and small
252 vertical deflections at the apex sections, as shown in Figure 3, although the deflections observed varied
253 remarkably for the different dead load levels considered. The cross-sections adopted for these frames
254 comprised compact sections with low local cross-sectional slenderness values and considerable capacity
255 to redistribute stress inelastically for the austenitic and ferritic materials considered (Frames 1 and 5).
256 However, for the duplex stainless steel Frame 3, these same cross-section dimensions resulted in a
257 significantly higher local slenderness owing to the higher yield stress characterizing the EN 1.4462/
258 ASTM 2205 duplex grade, and therefore limited the stress redistribution capacity of the frame when
259 compared to Frames 1 and 5. Austenitic and ferritic Frames 1 and 5 failed showing spatial yielding at
260 the critical cross-sections. At wind load levels of around 80% of the ultimate loads, spatial plastic hinges
261 formed at the two column bases, and the failure of the frames occurred soon thereafter when plastic
262 hinges formed at the rafters near the eaves on the right. At the ultimate limit states, considerably high
263 stresses of about 1.50 and 1.35 times the yield stress were observed at the column bases for Frame 1
264 and Frame 5, respectively, due to strain-hardening. At later stages of frame deformations, local failures
265 were visible in the compressed areas of the columns near the base connections and at the right eave
266 connections. On the contrary, failure of the duplex stainless steel Frame 3 occurred after the column
267 bases reached stress levels equivalent to the enhanced yield stress at wind load values of about 90% of
268 the ultimate loads. Although this frame was capable of withstanding marginally higher loads, it failed

269 before any spread of yielding was observed at the right eave due to the limited redistribution capacity
270 of the cross-section.

271 Frames 2, 4 and 6 exhibited relatively long spans and more slender cross-sections. These frames also
272 showed significant lateral drifts in their ultimate states, and vertical deflections at the apex sections
273 were larger than for the frames with shorter spans. The failure mode for Frame 4, typical for the long
274 span frames analysed, is shown in Figure 3. While the RHS sections corresponding to austenitic and
275 ferritic stainless steel alloys (Frames 2 and 6) had local slenderness values close to the limit between
276 slender and fully effective sections, the nominal cross-section in the duplex Frame 4 was a slender
277 section under compression. Consequently, these sections were incapable of developing strain-hardening
278 or bending moment redistribution. Failure of Frames 2, 4 and 6 occurred when the capacities of the
279 column bases and right eaves were reached, which corresponded to stress levels similar to the
280 corresponding nominal enhanced yield stress for Frames 2 and 6, but to considerably lower stresses for
281 Frame 4 due to the interaction with local buckling. For each frame, the failure of the three critical
282 sections occurred for very similar wind load levels. Due to the larger spans adopted for these frames,
283 significant flexural deformations and stresses were observed at the central parts of the left rafters at
284 their respective ultimate limit states, particularly for Frame 4 and Frame 6 (see Figure 3).

285 **4. SYSTEM STRENGTH RELIABILITY CALIBRATIONS**

286 This Section presents the statistical models adopted in the reliability calibration, including the main
287 random variables affecting the system strength of stainless steel structures, model uncertainties and
288 loads. The Section also describes the methodology adopted in the system reliability analysis of frames
289 subjected to combined gravity and wind loads for the three design frameworks investigated, i.e., the
290 Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks.

291 **4.1. STATISTICS OF THE UNCERTAIN VARIABLES AFFECTING THE STRENGTH**

292 Defining appropriate stochastic models for system strength distributions of actual stainless steel frames
293 subjected to combined gravity and wind loads is fundamental for the calibration of the system partial
294 safety factors and system resistance factors. These statistical models were estimated from extensive
295 numerical simulations accounting for the variability of different material, imperfection and geometric
296 random characteristics affecting the strength of stainless steel frames, as well as uncertainties associated

297 with FE simulations. The statistical models assumed for the variability of the random variables are
298 discussed in [21], and only a brief summary is provided herein.

299 The stochastic models for the variability of material parameters, cross-section geometric properties,
300 imperfections (at frame, member and local levels) and residual stresses considered in this study were
301 specific to cold-formed stainless steel members [22] and identical to those adopted in [21]. It is
302 important to highlight that the yield overstrength ratios (i.e., mean-to-nominal yield stress ratios)
303 reported in [22] for cold-formed stainless steel materials are significantly high, with $\bar{f}_y/f_{y,n}$ ratios being
304 1.30 for austenitic and ferritic families and 1.15 for duplex alloys. Due to the limited availability of real
305 measurements on frame imperfections for stainless steel frames, this study assumed the stochastic
306 variability of the out-of-plumb angle ϕ adopted in [14] for cold-formed steel frames. Likewise,
307 uncertainties associated with the behaviour of stainless steel stiffened welded connections were also
308 defined based on the data available for steel connections [14], since the measurements to characterize
309 the variability of the K_1 , K_2 , M_1 and M_2 parameters for stainless steel joints were deemed to be
310 insufficient [21]. The last stochastic variable affecting the resistance of stainless steel frames considered
311 in this study was model uncertainty γ_{FE} or θ , and accounted for the approximations and assumptions
312 made when determining the strength of structural systems using advanced FE simulations. Given the
313 reduced number of experimental results available for stainless steel frames, insufficient to derive a
314 specific probabilistic characterization of the model uncertainties, these were accounted for through
315 unbiased log-normal distributions with a COV of 0.05 [42,43].

316 Assuming that the variability of the overall frame properties was negligible in comparison with the
317 variability of other variables included in the analysis, such as loads and material properties, this analysis
318 and the study presented in [21] considered frame spans, column heights and heights at apex sections as
319 deterministic variables. In addition, the parameters governing the behaviour of connections and the
320 amplitudes and directions of member and local imperfections were considered as uncorrelated random
321 variables, while material properties, residual stress magnitudes and cross-sectional properties were
322 assumed to be perfectly correlated between all members. This last approach was found to be a
323 conservative assumption for reliability evaluations in [10], where the effect of the spatial correlation of

324 the material properties on the system reliability was investigated. The study considered perfectly-
325 correlated, uncorrelated and partially-correlated member properties, and concluded that while the mean-
326 to-nominal strength ratios were very similar in all cases, the COV values reduced for decreasing
327 correlation, with an extent depending on whether serial or parallel system effects are dominant.
328 Nevertheless, the final system resistance factors calibrated were found not to be affected by the degree
329 of correlation in member properties, although this finding is dependent on the redundancy of the system.

330 4.2. LOAD STATISTICS

331 The adoption of probabilistic models representing the maximum load to occur within a reference period
332 is fundamental to evaluate system reliability. This study is based on a reference period of 50 years,
333 which corresponds to the design service life for typical building structures and to which the stochastic
334 models available in the literature generally correspond. Statistical models adopted in the literature for
335 dead (or permanent) loads and wind loads in the different design frameworks investigated tend to be
336 consistent in terms of the distribution types adopted, but show different mean-to-nominal and COV
337 values, especially for wind loads. In general, dead loads are assumed to be normally distributed for the
338 three design frameworks [42-44], with mean-to-nominal values equal or very close to unity and small
339 coefficients of variation, as shown in Table 2.

340 Gravity loads can be governing in the design of stainless steel frames, especially imposed loads, but
341 it is usually the wind loading that has major influence in the final solution adopted. Nominal wind loads
342 calculated from the different wind loading standards depend on a number of parameters, as discussed
343 in Section 3.1. All these parameters are random in nature and are usually difficult to estimate since they
344 require extensive measurement databases to be calibrated, and consequently, they are recurrently
345 updated as more data becomes available, modifying the wind load probabilistic models [45]. The wind
346 load of interest in reliability analysis is the maximum wind load to occur within the reference period
347 defined for the study (denoted by W_{\max}), which in this case corresponds to 50 years. Traditionally,
348 loading standards have specified nominal or design wind loads using the wind speeds corresponding to
349 a return period of $T = 50$ years, denoted by $V_{n,50}$. Thus, the mean values of the maximum wind load

350 W_{\max} corresponding to a reference period of 50 years have been historically expressed using the
351 nominal winds for a return period of $T = 50$ years, $W_{n,50}$.

352 Wind speeds are generally assumed to follow Extreme Type I distributions, although wind loads
353 depend not only on the squares of wind speed, according to the models described in Section 3.1, but
354 also on a series of additional random parameters. Thus, the derivation of the probabilistic distribution
355 describing the wind load W_{\max} is not direct. The approach followed by Ellingwood et al. [46] was to
356 compute the cumulative probability distribution of the wind load function given in Eq. 6 numerically,
357 assuming that each component in the wind loading chain was an independent random variable and
358 assigning probabilistic distributions to each of them. The study used wind speed data from different
359 sites and assumed that the gust factor G , the pressure coefficient C_p and the exposure factor K_z followed
360 unbiased normal distributions. The distribution for the wind load was estimated through Monte Carlo
361 simulation and fitted to the 90th percentile and above by an Extreme Type I distribution with a mean-
362 to-nominal wind load ratio of 0.90 and a COV of 0.35. This wind load model has been systematically
363 used in the calibration of the load factors of the different editions of the ASCE 7 Specification.
364 However, recent studies have shown that a certain bias exists in the directionality factor, and the wind
365 load model derived in [46] was updated to account for this bias, reducing the mean value of the wind
366 load to $0.75W_{n,50}$ while keeping the COV constant [45], as reported in Table 2. A similar approach was
367 adopted in [47] when deriving the statistics for the wind loads in Australia, also resulting in an Extreme
368 Type I distribution with a mean value of the maximum wind load equal to $0.68W_{n,50}$ and a COV of 0.39.

369 With the aim of determining the wind load distributions in the Eurocode framework, a Monte Carlo
370 simulation was carried out in this paper following the methodology adopted in [46], but using the $W =$
371 $q_{\text{ref}} \cdot c_e \cdot c_p \cdot c_g$ wind load model and the statistics for the different wind load components reported in
372 Table 3. Note that while the peak velocity pressure q_{ref} represents the time-variant part of the wind
373 load model and depends on the wind climate, the rest of the factors constitute the time-invariant part of
374 the model, which convert the wind pressure into a wind loading on the structure. Additional
375 uncertainties have been considered through the model coefficient, as in [42]. For the time-invariant part
376 of the model the distributions based on recent studies by Botha et al. [48,49], and reported in Table 3,

377 were considered, which concluded that the wind load components with the greatest effect on the total
 378 wind load uncertainty are the peak velocity pressure q_{ref} , the exposure factor c_e and the pressure
 379 coefficient c_p . New probabilistic models were also developed in [48], indicating that the existing wind
 380 load models underestimate the uncertainty of these time-invariant wind load components as reduced
 381 biases and larger variabilities were observed. The probabilistic models reported in Table 3 for c_e and
 382 c_p are based on the combination of the new models derived in [48] and the original models used in
 383 [42,50] to assess the Eurocode, following the approach adopted in [49]. The final fit of the cumulative
 384 probability distribution for the wind load above the 90th percentile resulted in an Extreme Type I
 385 distribution with a mean-to-nominal value of 0.72 and a COV value of 0.36, which is similar to the
 386 revised wind load statistics derived in [45] for the US framework and the models used for the assessment
 387 of the Eurocode in [42,51,52] (i.e., a mean value of $0.70W_{k,50}$ and a COV of 0.35).

388 Table 2 summarizes the statistics of the wind loads adopted for the different design frameworks
 389 considered. These results indicate that wind load statistics are comparable for the three different design
 390 frameworks considered. It shall be noted that the current versions of the US and Australian wind loading
 391 standards define the nominal wind speeds using significantly higher return periods (i.e., 700 or 500
 392 years). In contrast, wind actions calculated using prEN 1991-1-4 [37] are intended to be characteristic
 393 values corresponding to annual exceedance probabilities of 2%, which are closely equivalent to a return
 394 period of 50 years. The adoption of higher return periods in ASCE 7-16 [38] and AS/NZS 1170.2 [39]
 395 allowed for the “cyclone factors” to be eliminated in the new standards, but required a re-calibration of
 396 the models describing the statistics of W_{max} wind loads for these frameworks. For this, the approximate
 397 relationship between the nominal wind loads for a T-year return period W_T and the wind load for a 50-
 398 year return period W_{50} proposed in [45], and given by Eq. 8, can be used, which is valid for most of the
 399 non-hurricane-prone regions of the US (ASCE 7 [38]).

$$W_T = W_{50}[0.36 + 0.10 \cdot \ln(12T)]^2 \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

400
 401 Nominal wind loads codified in the ASCE 7-16 [38] Specification for Risk Category II structures
 402 correspond to a return period of $T = 700$ years, while the AS/NZS 1170.2 [39] Specification features

403 design wind speeds for a return period of 500 years for Importance Level 2 structures and 50-year
 404 service lives. Using Eq. 8, the relationships between $W_{n,50}$ and $W_{n,700}$ and $W_{n,500}$ can be evaluated,
 405 and from these the means of W_{\max} relative to the $W_{n,700}$ and $W_{n,500}$ nominal loads can be estimated
 406 using the mean-to- $W_{n,50}$ values reported in Table 2. For the ASCE 7-16 [38] Specification,
 407 $W_{n,700}/W_{n,50} = 1.60$ is obtained from Eq. 8, which results in a mean of W_{\max} equal to $0.75W_{n,50} =$
 408 $0.75 W_{n,700}/1.60 = 0.47W_{n,700}$. Although the W_T/W_{50} ratio depends on the local wind climate and
 409 Eq. 8 is valid for non-hurricane-prone regions of the US, in the absence of an equivalent expression for
 410 the extratropical regions in Australia the same relationship has been adopted to estimate the
 411 $W_{n,500}/W_{n,50}$ ratio. Hence, for the AS/NZS 1170.2 [39] Specification with a nominal wind load
 412 corresponding to a 500-years return period, $W_{n,500}/W_{n,50} = 1.51$ is obtained and the mean of W_{\max} is
 413 recalculated as $0.68W_{n,50} = 0.68 W_{n,500}/1.51 = 0.45W_{n,500}$. It is worth noting that the wind loads
 414 have remarkably similar statistics in the current ASCE 7-16 [38] and AS/NZS 1170.2 [39]
 415 specifications, with mean values of the maximum wind load W_{\max} around $0.45W_n - 0.47W_n$ and
 416 coefficients of variation of 0.35–0.39. In summary, while the wind load distributions adopted in this
 417 study for the US and Australian frameworks corresponded to these mean and COV values, a mean of
 418 the maximum wind load W_{\max} and COV equal to $0.72W_{k,50}$ and 0.36, corresponding to a 50-years
 419 return period, were considered for the Eurocode framework; all wind loads were modelled as Extreme
 420 Type I largest distributions.

421 4.3. SYSTEM RELIABILITY ANALYSIS METHOD

422 The failure of a structural system is usually quantified by its probability of failure P_f , which is
 423 traditionally measured through the reliability index β . The probability of failure P_f is related to the
 424 reliability index by $\beta = \Phi^{-1}(1 - P_f)$, where Φ^{-1} is the inverse standard normal distribution function
 425 [53,54]. Although Direct Monte Carlo simulation is often used as a method of evaluating structural
 426 reliability, it can be computationally too demanding in studies where nonlinear shell-element based
 427 simulations are performed. For this reason, the study presented in this paper was based on the simplified
 428 yet robust reliability analysis method introduced in [10,14]. This method relies on the characterization
 429 of the stochastic properties of the resistance of frames using random sampling techniques, which is then

430 compared with the wind loads to integrate the convolution integral and approximate the probability of
 431 failure of the system P_f or the reliability index β using MATLAB [55]. Instead of adopting the standard
 432 random sampling method, the implementation of the more efficient Latin-Hypercube sampling (LHS)
 433 technique allowed reducing the number of required simulations to typically 200 cases per frame and
 434 dead load case [14].

435 To complement the reliability calibrations of stainless steel frames under gravity loads carried out
 436 in [21], and since the design of steel portal frames is generally governed by load combinations that
 437 include wind loads, this study considered loading scenarios comprising combined dead and wind loads.
 438 According to [44], including live loads in reliability analyses has a negligible effect on the calibrated
 439 reliabilities except for those cases where nominal live-to-dead load ratios L_n/D_n are high and nominal
 440 wind-to-dead load ratios W_n/D_n are low, but in such cases gravity loads are found to govern the design
 441 of the frames. Furthermore, the frames considered in this study are often slab on grade, in which the
 442 live load is carried by the slab, and the roof live loads are not likely to be present in high wind speed
 443 ultimate limit state scenarios. The ultimate limit state load combinations for dead and wind loads
 444 according to the prEN 1990 [53], ASCE 7-16 [38] and AS/NZS 1170.0 [54] specifications are given by
 445 Eq. 9 to Eq. 11 for the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks, where G_k , D_n and G_n represent
 446 the characteristic (or nominal) dead loads and $W_{k,50}$ and $W_{n,i}$ correspond to the characteristic (or
 447 nominal) wind loads.

Eurocode framework:	$1.35G_k + 1.5W_{k,50}$	Eq. 9
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US framework:	$1.20D_n + W_{n,700}$	Eq. 10
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Australian framework:	$1.20G_n + W_{n,500}$	Eq. 11
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448 Nevertheless, the reliability of structural systems depends on the load ratios, obtaining different
 449 reliability index β values for varying live-to-dead load ratios [11,21] and for varying wind-to-gravity
 450 load ratios [11-14] since each loading type shows a different variability (see Table 2). To account for
 451 this effect, and in order to consider loading scenarios with different wind predominance, three different
 452 levels of design dead loads were considered in this study, defining load cases GW1, GW2 and GW3,
 453 which represent wind-to-dead load ratios ranging between 2.5 and 7. These dead loads corresponded to

455 dead-to-total load ratios of 0.10-0.33, which are values commonly adopted in practice for portal frames
456 under combined dead and wind load scenarios [14]. According to [56], low dead load ratios (or high
457 wind-to-total load ratios) are aligned with the lowest reliability indices and thus, the safety or resistance
458 factors calibrated using these load ratios correspond to the most unfavourable design situations. For
459 each frame and each design dead load, five values of the system safety factor $\gamma_{M,S}$ (1.00, 1.05, 1.15,
460 1.25 and 1.55) and five values of the system resistance factor ϕ_s (0.75, 0.80, 0.85, 0.90 and 0.95) were
461 considered to calibrate the associated system reliabilities. These values were chosen with the aim of
462 obtaining a range of reliability indices β between 2.50-3.80 for the Eurocode framework and between
463 2.50-3.00 for the US/Australian frameworks. Note that although according to Table 2 the dead loads
464 show a variability of 0.10, the numerical simulations carried out in this study treated the dead load as
465 deterministic, for simplicity and following a similar approach to that adopted in [14]. A prior analysis
466 on Frames 1 and 6 indicated that the impact of considering dead loads as random variables on the mean
467 and COV values of the strength distribution is minimal, with the differences in the calibrated β -values
468 being less than 1%. This is a result of the uncertainties associated with dead loads being significantly
469 smaller than those of wind loads (see Table 2).

470 **5. SYSTEM STRENGTH CALIBRATION RESULTS**

471 The results of the reliability calibrations carried out for stainless steel frames subjected to combined
472 gravity and wind loads are presented and discussed in this Section. First, system strength distributions
473 obtained for the six portal frames and the different dead load levels investigated are presented, and the
474 reliability calibration results corresponding to the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks are
475 subsequently reported and compared. Then, suitable values for system safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system
476 resistance factors ϕ_s are recommended for the direct design of stainless steel frames subjected to
477 combined gravity and wind loads for different target reliability indices. Finally, the calibrated system
478 safety factors are compared with the values obtained from the semi-probabilistic approach detailed in
479 prEN 1990 [53] and the solutions obtained using the *single-step* approach are compared with the
480 stainless steel frames designed using the traditional *two-step* approach in terms of material consumption.

481 5.1. SYSTEM STRENGTH OF STAINLESS STEEL FRAMES UNDER GRAVITY AND WIND LOADS

482 System lateral strength R_w distributions for stainless steel frames subjected to combined gravity and
483 wind loads were determined from extensive numerical simulations using the advanced FE models
484 presented in Section 2, which accounted for all the relevant uncertainties according to the stochastic
485 models described in Section 4.1. Ultimate frame loads were obtained from the load-lateral drift curves
486 determined from finite element simulations for the apex joints. Following the approach adopted in
487 previous studies [14,21,57], for frames showing load-lateral drift curves with a clearly defined peak
488 point the ultimate load was adopted as this peak load. Conversely, for frames with no clear peak point
489 in the load-lateral drift curves, the ultimate load was obtained as the load at which the stiffness of the
490 curve fell below 5% of the initial stiffness. For the six stainless steel frames, histograms including the
491 individual random system lateral strengths R_w were built for the different dead loads investigated (load
492 cases GW1, GW2 and GW3), from which the different stochastic models for $R_{w,i}$ were determined. All
493 system strength distributions were fitted by log-normal distributions using the Statistics and Machine
494 Learning Toolbox in MATLAB [55] based on the maximum likelihood method, and the resulting
495 distributions were evaluated using Anderson-Darling goodness-of-fit tests at the 5% significance level.
496 It should be noted that the choice of a log-normal distribution to model frame strength histograms is
497 consistent with the distributions adopted in previous studies for system strengths of steel and stainless
498 steel structures [10,13,14,21]. Figure 4 shows typical examples of the histograms obtained from the
499 system lateral strengths and the fitted log-normal distributions corresponding to the six frames
500 investigated for the load case GW1, representing the lowest wind-to-dead load ratio. It is worth noting
501 that since the system lateral strength distributions were derived from numerical simulations based on
502 probabilistic models for material, imperfection, geometric and connection characteristics calibrated
503 from actual stainless steel structures, they can be used to carry out reliability calibrations in the three
504 design frameworks considered in this study.

505 The mean values of the system lateral strengths \bar{R}_w and corresponding coefficients of variation $V_{R,w}$
506 for the three dead load cases are reported in Table 4 for the six baseline frames. The results in Table 4
507 indicate that the mean system lateral strengths \bar{R}_w increased as the dead loads applied decreased, since

508 the design wind load became more dominant. The results also suggest that the uncertainty (i.e., $V_{R,w}$
509 values) of the system lateral strengths under different dead load levels were very similar for the six
510 frames, but reduced slightly as the G_k or D_n values reduced. In general, comparable values of COV can
511 be observed for all frames, lying between 0.090 and 0.113, although the lowest values of uncertainty
512 were obtained for Frames 1, 3 and 5, which corresponded to frames with short spans and considerably
513 stocky cross-sections. Among the different stainless steel families investigated, duplex alloys (Frames 3
514 and 4) were found to show the lowest $V_{R,w}$ values.

515 The values of the characteristic or nominal FE wind loads W_k or W_n associated with the different
516 values of system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ or system resistance factors ϕ_s for the Eurocode, US and Australian
517 frameworks are presented in Table 5. Fifteen combinations of G_k and $\gamma_{M,s}$ (or D_n and ϕ_s) were
518 investigated per design framework for each frame, with a total of 45 cases per frame. Using the results
519 in Table 4 and Table 5, the mean resistance-to-nominal wind ratios \bar{R}_w/W_k and \bar{R}_w/W_n were calculated
520 for the six frames, and the average values corresponding to each dead load level (considering the
521 different $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s -factors analysed) are reported in the last columns of Table 4 for the three design
522 frameworks. These ratios show a significant difference between the Eurocode and the US/Australian
523 frameworks, with the \bar{R}_w/W_k ratios calculated for the Eurocode being remarkably higher for all the
524 frames. This is because the W_k and W_n values were determined such that the frames satisfied design
525 equations Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, which depend on the load combination prescribed for each design framework.
526 The prEN 1990 [53] load combination for wind loading given in Eq. 9 features a load factor $\gamma_w = 1.50$,
527 while this factor is equal to 1.0 in the ASCE 7-16 [38] and AS/NZS 1170.0 [54] standards (see Eq. 10
528 and Eq. 11) since the nominal loads in ASCE 7-16 and AS/NZS 1170.0 correspond to considerably higher
529 return periods, as discussed in Section 4.2. With higher prescribed nominal wind loads W_n , the \bar{R}_w/W_n
530 ratios obtained for the US/Australian frameworks were lower than for the Eurocode.

531 Analysing the mean resistance-to-nominal wind ratios for the Eurocode framework reported in Table
532 4 it is evident that austenitic and ferritic stainless steel frames (Frames 1, 2, 5 and 6) showed similar
533 strength reserves (i.e., \bar{R}_w/W_k ratios) due to the equivalent overstrength ratios (i.e., mean-to-nominal
534 yield stress ratios) exhibited by these materials. On the contrary, the values reported for duplex frames

535 (Frames 3 and 4) are lower, owing to their lower overstrength ratio. The nominal wind load W_n values
536 obtained for the US and Australian frameworks were very similar for all the frames investigated,
537 because the load combinations (see Eq. 10 and Eq. 11) and nominal FE models (material properties and
538 imperfections) adopted in the two frameworks were almost identical. However, the relative comparison
539 of the \bar{R}_w/W_n ratios reported for the six stainless steel frames within the US or Australian frameworks
540 shows that the lowest \bar{R}_w/W_n ratios were observed for duplex frames (Frames 3 and 4), followed by
541 ferritic frames (Frames 5 and 6) and austenitic frames (Frames 1 and 2). This can be explained by the
542 considerably lower nominal material properties defined in the ASCE 8 [7] and AS/NZS 4673 [8]
543 specifications for austenitic and duplex stainless steel alloys, which means that the overstrength ratios
544 corresponding to the nominal ASCE 8 and AS/NZS 4673 material properties are significantly higher
545 than the ratios obtained for the nominal properties prescribed in EN 10088-4 [26]. Overstrength ratios
546 corresponding to the ASCE 8 [7] and AS/NZS 4673 [8] nominal material properties would be around
547 1.45, 1.25 and 1.30 for the ASTM 304, ASTM 2205 and ASTM UNS S40977 stainless steel grades,
548 respectively, which align with the \bar{R}_w/W_n ratios for the different materials. Similar observations were
549 also reported for stainless steel frames under gravity loads in [21].

550 5.2. RELIABILITY CALIBRATION RESULTS FOR FRAMES UNDER GRAVITY AND WIND LOADS

551 System reliability indices β derived for stainless steel portal frames subjected to combined gravity and
552 wind loads for a period of reference of 50 years are presented in this Section. The results were obtained
553 following the methodology described in Section 4.3, the probabilistic models for system lateral
554 resistance presented in Section 5.1 and the appropriate stochastic models for wind loads for the three
555 design frameworks.

556 The system reliability indices β determined for the three dead load levels investigated for each
557 stainless steel frame and the different values of system safety factor $\gamma_{M,s}$ or system resistance factors
558 ϕ_s considered are presented in Figure 5 for the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks as $\beta -$
559 $\gamma_{M,s}$ and $\beta - \phi_s$ relationships. The results in Figure 5 demonstrate that the reliability indices β increased
560 with increasing system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ but decreased with increasing system resistance factors ϕ_s ,
561 since the resistance factor can be considered equivalent to the inverse of the safety factor. The relative

562 reliability indices obtained for the six stainless steel frames within each of the design frameworks were
563 consistent with the mean resistance-to-nominal wind ratios \bar{R}_w/W_k or \bar{R}_w/W_n presented and discussed
564 in Section 5.1 and with the overstrength ratios (i.e., mean-to-nominal yield stress ratios) characterizing
565 each stainless steel family. The lowest reliability indices were observed for duplex frames (Frames 3
566 and 4), followed by ferritic (Frames 5 and 6) and austenitic frames (Frames 1 and 2). While the results
567 for austenitic and ferritic frames were very similar in the Eurocode framework, owing to the same
568 overstrength ratios exhibited by these materials, the reliability indices derived for austenitic frames in
569 the US/Australian framework were remarkably higher. This is to be expected as the low nominal yield
570 stress values prescribed in ASCE 8 [7] and AS/NZS 4673 [8] for the EN 1.4301/ASTM 304 grades
571 resulted in higher mean-to-nominal resistance ratios than those observed for the Eurocode framework.

572 The differences in the reliability indices β shown in Figure 5 among the three design frameworks
573 investigated were in general smaller than those observed for the same frames under gravity loads only
574 [21] for equivalent $\gamma_{M,s}$ or ϕ_s factors. This can be attributed to the similarities in the stochastic definition
575 of the wind loads for the different design frameworks (see Table 2 for a return period of $T = 50$ years).
576 Despite return periods used in the definition of the nominal wind loads in prEN 1991-1-4 [37], ASCE 7-
577 16 [38] and AS/NZS 1170.2 [39] being different, as discussed in Section 4.2, it should be noted that the
578 nominal wind loads in the wind-dominated load combinations prescribed in prEN 1990 [53], ASCE 7-
579 16 [38] and AS/NZS 1170.0 [54], and shown in Eq. 9 to Eq. 11, are multiplied by different load factors:
580 while the characteristic wind loads in the Eurocode are multiplied by a load factor of $\gamma_W = 1.50$,
581 nominal wind loads adopt a load factor equal to unity in the US and Australian frameworks. Coefficients
582 relating wind loads for a return period of $T = 50$ years and the nominal return periods in ASCE 7-16
583 [38] and AS/NZS 1170.2 [39] are, as calculated in Section 4.2, $W_{700}/W_{50} = 1.60$ and $W_{500}/W_{50} =$
584 1.51 , respectively, which are similar to the $\gamma_W=1.50$ factor adopted in the Eurocode. Hence, the final
585 wind loads adopted for the reliability calibrations in the three design frameworks are comparable and
586 produced similar values of reliability indices β .

587 Figure 5 also shows the average $\beta - \gamma_{M,s}$ and $\beta - \phi_s$ curves derived in [21] for stainless steel frames
588 under gravity loads only. The comparison of the reliability indices corresponding to gravity loads and

589 to combined gravity and wind loads showed that differences exist in structural reliability for different
590 load combinations; this is a well-known fact for the three design frameworks investigated [44,58-62].
591 This safety differentiation with respect to the type of loading was attributed to economic reasons and to
592 the fact that the wind load models contained many conservative assumptions for the Eurocode
593 [56,61,62]. Likewise, different authors have highlighted the fact that the reliability indices obtained for
594 the US and Australian frameworks by calibration to existing and acceptable designs for wind is less
595 than that for structures in which gravity loads govern [11,12,44,58,59].

596 5.3. DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

597 This Section presents a discussion on the appropriate target reliability indices β_0 for structures
598 dominated by wind loads and, based on these β_0 -values, provides recommendations for the system
599 safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ and resistance factors ϕ_s to be adopted in the direct design of stainless steel frames
600 subjected to combinations of gravity and wind loads.

601 The minimum value of the target reliability index recommended in prEN 1990 [53] for ultimate limit
602 states in RC2 reliability class structures and a 50-years reference period is $\beta_0 = 3.8$, which is commonly
603 considered in the reliability analyses carried out for the Eurocode framework [19,41,63]. Although the
604 reliability indices obtained for members through the traditional member-based design methodology are
605 not directly comparable to those corresponding to system-based design approaches, and the β_0 -values
606 in prEN 1990 [53] generally correspond to member-based design, the same target value has been
607 preliminarily adopted in this study. In statically determinate frames, or when failure occurs in a statically
608 determinate part of a redundant frame, the target reliability of member-based and system-based
609 approaches should be the same. In the case of statically redundant frames, where system-based
610 methodologies account for the additional frame capacity arising from the load redistribution after the
611 critical member reaches its capacity, the system target reliability index should be chosen to be at least
612 that of the member-based methodology. Likewise, ASCE 7-16 [38] prescribes different target reliability
613 indices depending on the Risk Category of the structure and the failure mode considered. For Risk
614 Categories I and II structures showing failure modes that are not sudden and do not lead to wide-spread
615 progression of damage, which is the case for the frames analysed in this paper, the prescribed target

616 reliabilities are $\beta_0 = 2.5$ and $\beta_0 = 3.0$, respectively, for reference periods of 50 years. For non-ductile
617 failure modes, including the failure of columns and connections, ASCE 7-16 requires higher target
618 reliabilities.

619 Considering that Figure 5 reports the reliability results for different wind-to-dead load ratios for each
620 system safety factor $\gamma_{M,s}$ and system resistance factor ϕ_s considered, and that for a given safety or
621 resistance factor the markers for the different wind-to-dead load ratios are hardly discernible, it can be
622 concluded that the wind-to-dead load ratio has a negligible effect on the reliability index β . The required
623 factors for achieving the target reliability indices are also not the same for the different frames.
624 However, for design purposes a single value of $\gamma_{M,s}$ or ϕ_s is desirable and thus, average system
625 reliabilities were considered in this study with the aim of recommending safety and resistance factors.
626 Table 6 reports the average values of reliability indices β corresponding to the three levels of dead load
627 for each baseline frame, a reference period of 50 years and different system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ or system
628 resistance factors ϕ_s . Averaged values considering all frames are also provided for each $\gamma_{M,s}$ or ϕ_s -
629 factor. Using the reliability indices presented in Table 6, it is possible to determine the required system
630 safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_s for the target reliability indices associated with the
631 different design frameworks, which are reported in Table 7. The $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s values included in Table
632 7 were calculated using linear interpolation between the reliability indices β shown in Table 6 for each
633 of the six frames and a range of target reliability indices β_0 , from which the average values considering
634 all frames were determined. It is worth noting that some of the $\gamma_{M,s}$ -factors reported in Table 7 are
635 below unity, while values above unity can be found for the US and Australian frameworks, particularly
636 for the lowest β_0 -values considered. This can be explained by the \bar{R}_w/W_k and \bar{R}_w/W_n ratios obtained
637 for the investigated frames, which exhibited sufficient strength reserve to meet some of the lowest
638 reliability requirements without needing additional system factors ($\gamma_{M,s}$ or ϕ_s) to be adopted.

639 Since the required system resistance factors ϕ_s to meet a target reliability index β_0 of 3.0 ranged
640 between 0.87 and 0.98 for the different frames in the US framework, and between 0.85 and 0.96 in the
641 Australian framework (see Table 7), with respective average values of 0.91 and 0.90, a ϕ_s -factor of
642 0.90 is recommended for the US and Australian frameworks for combined gravity and wind load cases.

643 It is worth mentioning that for a similar target reliability index the ϕ_s factors recommended in [21] for
644 gravity loads only were 0.95 and 0.90 for the US and Australian frameworks, respectively. The ϕ_s -
645 factors corresponding to a target value of about $\beta_0 = 2.50$ proposed in previous studies for steel frames
646 subjected to combined gravity and wind loads in the US framework were $\phi_s = 0.80 - 0.85$ for hot-
647 rolled planar frames [11], $\phi_s = 0.85$ for hot-rolled spatial frames [12], $\phi_s = 0.85 - 0.90$ for cold-
648 formed spatial frames [13] and $\phi_s = 0.85$ for cold-formed portal frame with locally unstable members
649 [14]. These values are more conservative than the ϕ_s -factors calibrated herein due to the higher mean-
650 to-nominal resistance ratios obtained for stainless steel frames as a result of the higher mean-to-nominal
651 yield stress ratios.

652 Similarly, the required system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ for the target reliability index of $\beta_0 = 3.8$
653 prescribed in prEN 1990 [53] ranged between 1.48 and 1.63, with an average value of $\gamma_{M,s} = 1.55$,
654 according to the values reported in Table 7. This is a significantly high safety factor compared to the
655 $\gamma_{M0} = \gamma_{M1} = 1.10$ values recommended in the current prEN 1993-1-4 [5] standard for the traditional
656 design of stainless steel cross-sections and members. It is also remarkably higher than the value
657 recommended in [21] for gravity loads only, $\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15$. The high $\gamma_{M,s}$ -values are due to the fact that
658 the load factor prescribed for wind loads in the Eurocode is insufficient to guarantee the required level
659 of reliability for reasonable values of partial safety factors; the need for load factors γ_W higher than the
660 prescribed value of 1.50 for wind and snow loads in the Eurocode framework has been already
661 highlighted in [49,60], which is equivalent to considering that the actual reliability index β_0 for wind
662 loading is lower than 3.8. An estimation of the required γ_W -factor to achieve a β_0 -value of 3.8 can be
663 obtained from Eq. 12, which provides the relationship between the design load and the mean load for
664 different fractile levels corresponding to failure probabilities of P_f for Gumbel distributions – note that
665 $P_f = \Phi(-\beta)$ [49]. Considering that the load factor for wind is defined as $\gamma_W = W_d/W_k$ and that the
666 mean-to-characteristic load ratio \bar{W}/W_k is already known from Section 4.2, a relationship between γ_W
667 and P_f (or β) can be derived. Using the sensitivity factor $\alpha_E = 0.7$ prescribed in the Eurocode for loads
668 [53], the wind load factor required to meet a level of reliability of $\alpha_E \cdot \beta_0 = 0.7 \cdot 3.8 = 2.66$ is $\gamma_W =$
669 1.73, which is significantly higher than the 1.50 codified value.

$$W_d/\bar{W} = 1 - 0.45V_W - 0.78V_W \ln(-\ln(1 - P_f)) \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

670
671 In view of this, there are two possible alternatives to calibrate a system safety factor for gravity plus
672 wind load cases: (i) recognizing that the $\gamma_W = 1.50$ value prescribed in prEN 1990 [53] is not sufficient
673 to meet a target reliability of $\beta_0 = 3.8$, a new value of the γ_W -factor can be derived to ensure that the
674 required reliability criteria is met, which is the approach followed by Botha et al. [49] for the South
675 African specification; or (ii) acknowledge that the level of reliability achieved for wind loads using a
676 γ_W -factor of 1.50 is lower than that for gravity load scenarios and insufficient to guarantee the target
677 reliability requirements [49,60], and thus to adopt a reduced target reliability to calibrate a system safety
678 factor that is not too severe to achieve the full potential of system-based design approaches [64]. In this
679 paper the second alternative was adopted in order to affect the design framework that is familiar to
680 practicing engineers as little as possible, since while load factors are well-assimilated by designers, it
681 is common to adopt a range of partial safety factors when working with different materials or failure
682 modes. A reasonable reduced value for the target reliability index would be that adopted for the US and
683 Australian design frameworks for wind load dominated structures, i.e., $\beta_0 = 3.0$. In this case, and
684 according to the values reported in Table 7, the required $\gamma_{M,S}$ -factors range between 1.14 and 1.28, with
685 an average value of 1.20. Hence, a system safety factor of $\gamma_{M,S} = 1.20$ is recommended for stainless
686 steel frames under gravity plus wind load cases.

687 5.4. CALIBRATION USING THE EUROCODE SEMI-PROBABILISTIC APPROACH

688 To calibrate the $\gamma_{M,S}$ -factor using the standard semi-probabilistic method given in prEN 1990 [53] Eq.
689 13 should be used, in which the R_k/\bar{R}_W -ratio accounts for the bias in the strength function. Considering
690 that the average R_k/\bar{R}_W -ratio for the different frames is 1.13, that the sensitivity factor prescribed in
691 the Eurocode is $\alpha_R = 0.8$ for resistance [53], and adopting a target reliability index of $\beta_0 = 3.8$, the
692 average estimated system safety factor is $\gamma_{M,S} = 1.41$, different from the $\gamma_{M,S} = 1.55$ value calibrated
693 in Section 5.2 for the same target reliability. This is because, as highlighted above, the actual level of
694 reliability obtained for a load factor of $\gamma_W = 1.50$ is lower than the target value of 3.8. If the actual β
695 (or P_f) is back-calculated from Eq. 12 for the wind load model adopted in this study, one obtains a
696 reliability index of 3.2. The system safety factor resulting from Eq. 13 for this value of β is $\gamma_{M,S} = 1.15$,

697 which differs by 10% from the value derived using the results in Table 6 for a corresponding value of
698 $\beta_0 = 3.2$, $\gamma_{M,s} = 1.27$, in line with the findings reported in [65].

$$\gamma_{M,s} = (R_k/\bar{R}_w)\exp(\alpha_R\beta_0V_{R,w}) \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

699 An alternative procedure would have been to re-run the reliability analyses described in Section 5.2 for
700 the $\gamma_w = 1.73$ value derived in the previous Section, and to use the resulting values to calibrate the
701 system safety factor $\gamma_{M,s}$ for a target reliability index of $\beta_0 = 3.8$. Since the use of $\gamma_w = 1.73$ would
702 result in higher reliability indices than those reported in Table 6, the required $\gamma_{M,s}$ -factor would be lower
703 than the 1.55 value shown in Table 7 and comparable to the $\gamma_{M,s} = 1.41$ value obtained at the beginning
704 of this Section.
705

706 5.5. COMPARISON WITH TRADITIONAL TWO-STEP DESIGN SOLUTIONS

707 In order to quantify the differences between stainless steel frames designed using the *single-step* direct
708 approach developed in this paper and the traditional *two-step* approach in terms of material
709 consumption, the different frames were re-designed using the provisions given in prEN 1993-1-4 [5],
710 ASCE 8 [7] and AS/NZS 4673 [8]. For this comparison, the design loads W_{Ed} for each frame were
711 defined as the ultimate nominal lateral strengths of the frames divided or multiplied by the $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s -
712 factors recommended in this paper (i.e., $W_{Ed} = W_k/\gamma_{M,s}$ and $W_{Ed} = \phi_s \cdot W_n$). Hence, it was assumed
713 that the six baseline frames were precisely at their ultimate limit states under the design loads W_{Ed} , and
714 the cross-section dimensions required to withstand these loads were determined using the *two-step*
715 approach. The final designs corresponding to the traditional *two-step* approach are reported in Table 8.
716 Note that the differences between the two design approaches would be larger in practice, since in this
717 comparison only the strictly minimum section increases were determined with the aim of identifying
718 the gains directly attributable to the use of the direct design approach, resulting in non-commercial
719 cross-section shapes and thickness values, as indicated in Table 8.

720 According to these results, the frames designed using the traditional *two-step* approach required
721 14.3%, 16.1% and 15.6% more material consumption, on average, than the direct design approach for
722 the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks, respectively. The differences are larger for the

723 US and Australian frameworks because for these frameworks the recommended system ϕ_s -factors are
724 equal to those codified in the codes for beams and columns (ϕ_c and ϕ_b) in [7,8], while the partial safety
725 factor proposed for systems $\gamma_{M,s}$ in this paper is more conservative than the $\gamma_{M,0}$ and $\gamma_{M,1}$ values given
726 in prEN 1993-1-4 [5]. It is also worth mentioning that, due to the low compression forces occurring in
727 the columns for the investigated frames, the limiting strength check in all cases was the bending moment
728 resistance of the critical cross-sections. The design equations for bending moment strength prescribed
729 in prEN 1993-1-4 [5], ASCE 8 [7] and AS/NZS 4673 [8] tend to estimate the capacity of cross-sections
730 better than the strength of members, and hence it is expected that the differences in material
731 consumption between the two design approaches may be higher for structures showing member failure
732 modes.

733 5.6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SPECIFICATION COMMITTEES

734 Based on the results presented in this paper and the equivalent study for stainless steel frames under
735 gravity loads reported in [21], two different sets of recommendations exist for each design framework
736 in terms of system safety and resistance factors. Prescribing resistance factors that depend on the load
737 combination would be, however, impractical from an implementation point of view. Considering the
738 system factors calibrated for the two load combinations, it is preliminarily recommended to adopt the
739 values derived in this paper for gravity plus wind load cases for all load combinations. Although these
740 $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s values might be too conservative for gravity load cases, the practical consequences of this
741 decision are not expected to be too significant since the design of portal frames is generally governed
742 by wind loads [14]. Moreover, the system factors for gravity loads calibrated in [21] correspond to dead
743 and live (imposed) loads only, and do not consider other types of loads (i.e., snow loads) that exhibit
744 greater variability, which would potentially result in $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s -factors more similar to those derived
745 in this paper. Nevertheless, and considering that the choice of target reliability indices ultimately rests
746 with specification committees which may decide to require different target reliabilities for the ultimate
747 limit state of systems than for members, as the consequences of the collapse of a system may be more
748 severe than that of the failure of an individual member [64], Table 7 also reports system safety factors
749 $\gamma_{M,s}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_s for a range of β_0 values.

750 The $\gamma_{M,S}$ and ϕ_S factors recommended in this paper for stainless steel frames under combined gravity
751 and wind loads, and in [21] for gravity loads, are calibrated for the ultimate limit state check. However,
752 stainless steels exhibit a pronounced nonlinear stress vs strain behaviour with a gradual loss of stiffness
753 even for low values of strain and consequently, serviceability limit states require greater attention than
754 for steel structures. Independent reliability calibrations are thus necessary for serviceability, which are
755 currently underway.

756 **6. CONCLUSIONS**

757 The latest versions of the main international design codes for steel and stainless steel structures [1-4]
758 provide a basis for system-based design strategies by incorporating preliminary provisions of system-
759 based direct design approaches. These approaches represent a change in the paradigm of structural
760 design and will constitute the next generation of structural design standards, simplifying the design
761 process and potentially leading to more efficient and lighter structures. Recommendations for the use
762 of advanced direct design methods for steel structures have been already developed for different steel
763 structures, including hot-rolled frames, cold-formed frames, racks and scaffolding structures. This study
764 is part of a research effort to extend system-based direct design methods to stainless steel structures.
765 The reliability framework for the design of stainless steel frames using advanced nonlinear numerical
766 simulations was developed in [21,22], and was used in this paper. While [21] primarily focused on
767 gravity loads, this study presents the system reliability calibrations for stainless steel portal frames
768 subjected to combined gravity and wind loads.

769 The system reliability calibrations presented in this paper are based on extensive finite element
770 simulations of six stainless steel portal frames covering austenitic, duplex and ferritic stainless steel alloys,
771 which accounted for the effect of uncertainties in geometric properties, imperfections, residual stresses,
772 material properties, connection stiffness and model uncertainty. The results showed that system reliability
773 indices β derived for the European, US and Australian design frameworks for a reference period of 50
774 years were similar and consistent for the three frameworks, but lower than those derived under gravity
775 loads [21]. Thus, different and slightly more conservative system factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and ϕ_S were recommended
776 for wind-dominated load cases. The results suggested that a system safety factor of $\gamma_{M,S} = 1.20$ is

777 appropriate for the Eurocode framework to achieve a reduced target reliability index of $\beta_0 = 3.0$, while a
778 resistance factor of $\phi_s = 0.90$ may be adopted for the US and Australian frameworks for a target
779 reliability index of $\beta_0 = 3.0$. Since the choice of target reliability indices ultimately rests with
780 specification committees, the tabulated values of system factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s for a range of target reliability
781 index values β_0 reported in this paper can be of assistance to these committees in choosing suitable values
782 of $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s corresponding to selected β_0 -values.

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786 **REFERENCES**

- 787 [1] AS/NZS 4100 Steel Structures. Standards Australia, Sydney, Australia, 2020.
- 788 [2] American Institute of Steel Construction (ANSI/AISC). AISC 360. Specification for Structural Steel
789 Buildings. Illinois, USA, 2016.
- 790 [3] American Institute of Steel Construction (ANSI/AISC). AISC 370. Specification for Structural
791 Stainless Steel Buildings. Illinois, USA, 2021.
- 792 [4] Working Group 22 for Eurocode 3, CEN/TC 250/SC3/WG22. prEN 1993-1-14. Eurocode 3: Design of
793 steel structures – Part 1-14: Design assisted by finite element analysis. Brussels, Belgium. *Under development*.
- 794 [5] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1993-1-4. Eurocode 3: Design of Steel
795 Structures – Part 1-4: General Rules. Supplementary Rules for Stainless Steels. Final Document.
796 Brussels, Belgium, 2020.
- 797 [6] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1993-1-1. Eurocode 3: Design of Steel
798 Structures – Part 1-1: General Rules and Rules for Buildings. Final Document. Brussels, Belgium, 2019.
- 799 [7] American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE). SEI/ASCE 8. Specification for the Design of Cold-
800 Formed Stainless Steel Structural Members. Virginia, USA, 2021.
- 801 [8] AS/NZS 4673 Cold-formed stainless steel structures. Standards Australia, Sydney, Australia, 2001.

802 [9] Zhang H., Liu H., Ellingwood B.R. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System reliabilities of planar gravity steel
803 frames designed by the inelastic method in AISC 360-10. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)*
804 144(3):04018011, 2018.

805 [10] Zhang H., Shayan S., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Ellingwood B.R. System-based design of planar steel
806 frames, I: Reliability framework. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 123, 135–143, 2016.

807 [11] Zhang H., Shayan S., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Ellingwood B.R. System-based design of planar steel
808 frames, II: Reliability results and design recommendations. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*
809 123, 154–161, 2016.

810 [12] Liu W., Zhang H., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Yan S. System-based limit state design criterion for 3D
811 steel frames under wind loads. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 157, 440–449, 2019.

812 [13] Liu W., Zhang H. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System reliability-based Direct Design Method for space
813 frames with cold-formed steel hollow sections. *Engineering Structures* 166, 79–92, 2018.

814 [14] Sena Cardoso F., Zhang H., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Yan S. Reliability calibrations for the design
815 of cold-formed steel portal frames by advanced analysis. *Engineering Structures* 182, 164–171, 2019.

816 [15] Sena Cardoso F., Zhang H. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System reliability-based criteria for the design
817 of steel storage rack frames by advanced analysis: Part II – Reliability analysis and design applications.
818 *Thin-Walled Structures* 141, 725–739, 2019.

819 [16] Wang C., Zhang H., Rasmussen K.J.R., Reynolds J. and Yan S. Reliability-based limit state design
820 of support scaffolding systems. *Engineering Structures* 216, 110677, 2020.

821 [17] Baddoo N.R. Stainless steel in construction: A review of research, applications, challenges and
822 opportunities. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 64(11), 1199–1206, 2008.

823 [18] Gardner L. Stability and design of stainless steel structures – Review and outlook. *Thin-Walled*
824 *Structures* 141, 208–216, 2019.

825 [19] Afshan S., Francis P., Baddoo N.R. and Gardner L. Reliability analysis of structural stainless steel
826 design provisions. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 114, 293–304, 2015.

827 [20] NewGeneSS, New Generation Design Methods for Stainless Steel Structures. Marie Skłodowska-
828 Curie Fellowship 2018, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation
829 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 842395.

830 [21] Arrayago I. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System-based reliability analysis of stainless steel frames under
831 gravity loads. *Engineering Structures* 231, 111775, 2021.

832 [22] Arrayago I., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Real E. Statistical analysis of the material, geometrical and
833 imperfection characteristics of structural stainless steels and members. *Journal of Constructional Steel*
834 *Research* 175, 106378, 2020.

835 [23] Arrayago I., Real E. and Gardner L. Description of stress-strain curves for stainless steel alloys.
836 *Materials & Design* 87, 540–552, 2015.

837 [24] Rasmussen K.J.R. Full-range stress-strain curves for stainless steel alloys. *Journal of*
838 *Constructional Steel Research* 59(1), 47–61, 2003.

839 [25] Steel Construction Institute (SCI). Design Manual for Structural Stainless Steel. Fourth Edition.
840 UK, 2017.

841 [26] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). EN 10088-4. Stainless Steels Part 4: Technical
842 Delivery Conditions for Sheet/Plate and Strip of Corrosion Resisting Steels for Construction Purposes.
843 Brussels, Belgium, 2009.

844 [27] Rossi B., Afshan S. and Gardner L. Strength enhancements in cold-formed structural sections –
845 Part II: Predictive models. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 83, 189–196, 2013.

846 [28] Packer J.A., Wardenier J., Kurobane Y., Dutta D. and Yeomans N. Design guide for rectangular
847 hollow section (RHS) joints under predominantly static loading. CIDECT Design Guide No. 3. Verlag
848 TÜV Rheinland GmbH, Köln, Germany, 1992.

849 [29] ABAQUS. Version 6.10. Simulia, Dassault Systèmes, France, 2010.

850 [30] Arrayago I., Picci F., Mirambell E. and Real E. Interaction of bending and axial load for ferritic
851 stainless steel RHS columns. *Thin-Walled Structures* 91, 96–107, 2015.

852 [31] Becque J. and Rasmussen K.J.R. A numerical investigation of local-overall interaction buckling of
853 stainless steel lipped channel columns. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 65, 1685–1693, 2009.

854 [32] Arrayago I., González-de-León I., Real E. and Mirambell E. Tests on stainless steel frames. Part
855 II: Results and analysis. *Thin-Walled Structures* 157, 107006, 2020.

856 [33] Gardner L. and Nethercot D.A. Numerical modelling of stainless steel structural components – A
857 consistent approach. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 130(10), 1586–1601, 2004.

858 [34] Gardner L. and Cruise R.B. Modeling of residual stresses in structural stainless steel sections.
859 *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 135(1), 42–53, 2009.

860 [35] Olsson A. Constitutive modelling of stainless steel. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 46:1-
861 3, Paper No. 242, 1998.

862 [36] Arrayago I., González-de-León I., Real E. and Mirambell E. Tests on stainless steel frames. Part I:
863 Preliminary tests and experimental set-up. *Thin-Walled Structures* 157, 107005, 2020.

864 [37] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1991-1-4. Eurocode 1: Actions on
865 structures – Part 1-4: Wind Actions. Final Document. Brussels, Belgium, 2019.

866 [38] American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE). ASCE 7. Minimum design loads and associated
867 criteria for buildings and other structures. Virginia, USA, 2016.

868 [39] AS/NZS 1170.2 Structural design actions, Part 2: Wind actions. Standards Australia, Sydney,
869 Australia, 2011.

870 [40] Kwon D.K. and Kareem A. Comparative study of major international wind codes and standards
871 for wind effects on tall buildings. *Engineering Structures* 51, 23–35, 2013.

872 [41] Taras A. and Huemer S. On the influence of the load sequence on the structural reliability of steel
873 members and frames. *Structures* 4, 91–104, 2015.

874 [42] Gulvanessian H. and Holicky M. Eurocodes: using reliability analysis to combine action effects.
875 *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers, Structures & Buildings* 158(SB4), 243–252, 2005.

876 [43] Joint Committee on Structural Safety (JCSS). Probabilistic Model Code. Zurich, Switzerland, 2001.

877 [44] Ellingwood B.R. and Tekie P.B. Wind load statistics for probability-based structural design.
878 *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 125(4), 453–463, 1999.

879 [45] McAllister T.P., Wang N. and Ellingwood B.R. Risk-informed mean recurrence intervals for
880 updated wind maps in ASCE 7-16. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 144(5):06018001, 2018.

881 [46] Ellingwood B.R., Galambos T.V., MacGregor J.G. and Cornell C.A. Development of a Probability
882 Based Load Criterion for American National Standard A58. National Bureau of Standards. Special
883 Publication No. 577. Washington D.C., 1980.

884 [47] Holmes J.D., Kwok K.C.S. and Ginger J.D. Wind loading handbook for Australia and New
885 Zealand-background to AS/NZS 1170.2 wind actions. Report No. AWES-HB-001-2012, Australian
886 Wind Engineering Society, 2012.

887 [48] Botha J., Retief J.V. and Viljoen C. Uncertainties in the South African wind load design
888 formulation. *Journal of the South African Institution of Civil Engineering* 60(3), 16–29, 2018.

889 [49] Botha J., Retief J.V. and Viljoen C. Reliability assessment of the South African wind load design
890 formulation. *Journal of the South African Institution of Civil Engineering* 60(3), 30–40, 2018.

891 [50] Holický M. Reliability Analysis for Structural Design. Stellenbosch: SUN MeDIA, ISBN 978-1-
892 920338-11-4, 2009.

893 [51] Holický M. and Marková J. Reliability of Concrete Elements Designed for Alternative Load
894 Combinations Provided in Eurocodes. *Acta Polytechnica* 43(1), 29–33, 2003.

895 [52] Development of skills facilitating implementation of Eurocodes. Handbook 2: Reliability
896 Backgrounds. Leonardo da Vinci pilot project CZ/02/B/F/PP-134007, 2005.

897 [53] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1990. Eurocode: Basis of Structural
898 Design. Draft Document. Brussels, Belgium, 2020.

899 [54] AS/NZS 1170.0 Structural design actions, Part 0: General principles. Standards Australia, Sydney,
900 Australia, 2002.

901 [55] MATLAB version 9.8.0 (R2020a). The MathWorks Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, 2020.

902 [56] Meinen N.E. and Steenbergen R.D.J.M. Reliability levels obtained by Eurocode partial factor
903 design - A discussion on current and future reliability levels. *HERON* 63(3), 243–302, 2018.

904 [57] Ziemian R.D., McGuire W. and Deierlein G.G. Inelastic limit states design. Part I: planar frame
905 studies. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 118(9), 2532–2549, 1992.

906 [58] Ellingwood B.R. LRFD: implementing structural reliability in professional practice. *Engineering*
907 *Structures* 22, 106–15, 2000.

908 [59] Ellingwood B.R. Probability-based codified design: past accomplishments and future challenges.
909 *Structural Safety* 13, 159–176, 1994.

910 [60] Joint Committee on Structural Safety (JCSS). Background Documentation Eurocode 1 (ENV 1991),
911 Part 1: Basis of Design. ECCS Report No. 94, 1996.

- 912 [61] Steenbergen R.D.J.M. and Vrouwenvelder A.C.W.M. Safety philosophy for existing structures and
913 partial factors for traffic loads on bridges. *HERON* 55(2), 123–140, 2010.
- 914 [62] Vrouwenvelder A.C.W.M. and Scholten N.P.M., Veiligheidsbeoordeling bestaande bouw,
915 Achtergrondrapport bij NEN 8700. TNO Report 2008-D-R0015, 2008.
- 916 [63] Steenbergen R.D.J.M. and Vrouwenvelder A.C.W.M. Safety philosophy for existing structures and
917 partial factors for traffic loads on bridges. *HERON* 55(2), 123–140, 2010.
- 918 [64] Zhang H., Ellingwood B.R. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System reliabilities in steel structural frame
919 design by inelastic analysis. *Engineering Structures* 81, 341–348, 2014.
- 920 [65] Arrayago I., Zhang H. and Rasmussen K.J.R. Simplified expressions for reliability assessments in
921 code calibration. *Submitted to Engineering Structures*, 2021.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Gravity and wind load patterns (adapted from [21]).

Figure 2. Nominal stress-strain curves for the different stainless steel alloys and design frameworks considered.

Figure 3. Typical failure modes for (a) short and (b) long span stainless steel frames under combined gravity and wind loads.

Figure 4. Typical histograms for system lateral strength of stainless steel frames under the GW1 dead and wind load case for Frames 1 to 6.

Figure 5. Calibrated $\beta - \gamma_{M,S}$ and $\beta - \phi_s$ relationships for stainless steel frames subjected to combined gravity and wind loads for the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks.

TABLES

Table 1. Key parameter definition of nominal frames (adapted from [21]).

Variable group	Variable	Austenitic stainless steel		Duplex stainless steel		Ferritic stainless steel	
		Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4	Frame 5	Frame 6
Overall frame geometry	s [m]	8.0	10.0	8.0	12.0	8.0	11.0
	H ₁ [m]	4.8	6.4	4.8	6.6	4.8	6.5
	H ₂ [m]	6.0	7.0	6.0	7.4	6.0	7.2
Joint behaviour at bases	K _{1,base} [kNm/rad]	4000	5000	4000	5000	4000	5000
	K _{2,base} [kNm/rad]	400	500	400	500	400	500
	M _{1,base} [kNm]	26.3	52.3	41.4	90.3	27.0	53.9
	M _{2,base} [kNm]	40.4	80.2	63.4	109.5	41.4	82.6
Joint behaviour at eaves	K _{1,eave} [kNm/rad]	6400	7000	6400	9000	6400	8000
	K _{2,eave} [kNm/rad]	640	700	640	900	640	800
	M _{1,eave} [kNm]	23.9	50.0	37.6	86.4	24.6	51.5
	M _{2,eave} [kNm]	37.4	78.2	58.7	105.4	38.4	80.5
Joint behaviour at apex	K _{1,apex} [kNm/rad]	6600	7500	6600	9500	6600	8500
	K _{2,apex} [kNm/rad]	660	750	660	950	660	850
	M _{1,apex} [kNm]	25.4	53.1	39.9	91.8	26.1	54.8
	M _{2,apex} [kNm]	37.4	78.2	58.7	105.4	38.4	80.5
Level of dead load	GW1 - G _k or D _n [kN/m]	1.00	1.40	2.00	2.00	1.00	1.60
	GW2 - G _k or D _n [kN/m]	0.75	1.20	1.50	1.60	0.75	1.40
	GW3 - G _k or D _n [kN/m]	0.60	1.00	1.00	1.40	0.60	1.20

Table 2. Statistics of loads.

Framework	Load type	Mean	COV	Statistical distribution	Reference
Eurocode framework	Dead load G	$1.00 \cdot G_k$	0.10	Normal	[42]
	Wind load W_{max}	$0.72 \cdot W_{k,50}^*$	0.36	Extreme Type I	-
US framework	Dead load D	$1.05 \cdot D_n$	0.10	Normal	[44]
	Wind load W_{max}	$0.75 \cdot W_{n,50}^*$	0.35	Extreme Type I	[45]
	Wind load W_{max}	$0.47 \cdot W_{n,700}^\dagger$	0.35	Extreme Type I	-
Australian framework	Dead load G	$1.05 \cdot G_n$	0.10	Normal	[21]
	Wind load W_{max}	$0.68 \cdot W_{n,50}^*$	0.39	Extreme Type I	[47]
	Wind load W_{max}	$0.45 \cdot W_{n,500}^\ddagger$	0.39	Extreme Type I	-

* Nominal wind load is based on a return period of T=50 years.

† Nominal wind load is based on a return period of T=700 years.

‡ Nominal wind load is based on a return period of T=500 years.

Table 3. Distributions of wind load components adopted in the derivation of the wind load model for the Eurocode framework.

Variable	Mean	COV	Statistical distribution	Reference
Basic wind pressure, q_{ref}	1.10	0.18	Extreme Type I	[42]
Roughness factor, c_e	0.84	0.12	Normal	[48]
Pressure coefficient, c_p	1.00	0.16	Normal	[48]
Gust factor, c_g	1.00	0.10	Normal	[42]
Model coefficient	0.80	0.20	Normal	[42]

Table 4. Statistics of system lateral strength for stainless steel frames subjected to combined gravity and wind loads.

Frame	G_k, D_n or G_n [kN/m]	\bar{R}_w [kN/m]	$V_{R,w}$	Eurocode	US	Australian
				framework \bar{R}_w/W_k	framework \bar{R}_w/W_n	framework \bar{R}_w/W_n
Frame 1	1.00	7.560	0.097	2.11	1.52	1.51
	0.75	7.584	0.097	2.08	1.50	1.50
	0.60	7.636	0.094	2.08	1.50	1.50
Frame 2	1.40	12.281	0.111	2.08	1.55	1.54
	1.20	12.368	0.110	2.08	1.55	1.54
	1.00	12.428	0.110	2.06	1.55	1.54
Frame 3	2.00	10.083	0.094	1.94	1.35	1.35
	1.50	10.154	0.093	1.92	1.34	1.34
	1.00	10.231	0.090	1.91	1.33	1.33
Frame 4	2.00	13.861	0.106	1.96	1.41	1.41
	1.60	13.898	0.104	1.90	1.37	1.37
	1.40	13.909	0.101	1.86	1.34	1.34
Frame 5	1.00	7.404	0.094	2.10	1.38	1.39
	0.75	7.452	0.093	2.08	1.37	1.38
	0.60	7.478	0.092	2.07	1.37	1.38
Frame 6	1.60	12.291	0.113	2.19	1.42	1.43
	1.40	12.355	0.113	2.16	1.41	1.42
	1.20	12.419	0.112	2.14	1.40	1.41

Table 5. Nominal system lateral strength for stainless steel frames subjected to combined gravity and wind loads for different system safety ($\gamma_{M,s}$) and resistance (ϕ_s) factors.

Design framework	Dead load case	$\gamma_{M,s}$ or ϕ_s	W_k or W_n [kN/m]					
			Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4	Frame 5	Frame 6
Eurocode framework	$G_{k,1}$	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.00$	4.37	7.18	6.34	8.79	4.30	6.91
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.05$	4.14	6.84	6.02	8.32	4.07	6.53
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15$	3.76	6.20	5.45	7.50	3.70	5.92
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.25$	3.44	5.66	5.00	6.78	3.39	5.40
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.55$	2.72	4.46	3.93	5.19	2.67	4.18
	$G_{k,2}$	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.00$	4.41	7.24	6.41	9.00	4.35	6.97
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.05$	4.20	6.89	6.08	8.52	4.12	6.64
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15$	3.82	6.25	5.53	7.74	3.76	6.01
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.25$	3.49	5.70	5.09	7.03	3.44	5.49
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.55$	2.79	4.53	4.05	5.46	2.75	4.29
	$G_{k,3}$	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.00$	4.44	7.34	6.47	9.17	4.37	7.08
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.05$	4.22	6.94	6.14	8.68	4.16	6.69
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15$	3.84	6.34	5.61	7.83	3.78	6.11
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.25$	3.53	5.79	5.14	7.16	3.48	5.57
		$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.55$	2.82	4.60	4.13	5.60	2.77	4.39
US framework	$D_{n,1}$	$\phi_s = 0.75$	4.41	6.99	6.58	8.56	4.74	7.60
		$\phi_s = 0.80$	4.70	7.53	7.04	9.26	5.08	8.17
		$\phi_s = 0.85$	5.03	8.00	7.51	9.98	5.40	8.75
		$\phi_s = 0.90$	5.35	8.47	8.01	10.64	5.75	9.33
		$\phi_s = 0.95$	5.65	9.01	8.46	11.30	6.06	9.93
	$D_{n,2}$	$\phi_s = 0.75$	4.46	7.06	6.70	8.92	4.81	7.72
		$\phi_s = 0.80$	4.78	7.53	7.15	9.58	5.13	8.30
		$\phi_s = 0.85$	5.08	8.06	7.63	10.25	5.48	8.88
		$\phi_s = 0.90$	5.38	8.54	8.10	10.93	5.81	9.41
		$\phi_s = 0.95$	5.68	9.01	8.55	11.61	6.13	10.01
	$D_{n,3}$	$\phi_s = 0.75$	4.51	7.12	6.80	9.11	4.84	7.84
		$\phi_s = 0.80$	4.81	7.59	7.26	9.78	5.19	8.43
		$\phi_s = 0.85$	5.11	8.06	7.71	10.46	5.51	8.95
		$\phi_s = 0.90$	5.44	8.61	8.20	11.14	5.84	9.55
		$\phi_s = 0.95$	5.75	9.09	8.65	11.76	6.16	10.08
Australian framework	$G_{n,1}$	$\phi_s = 0.75$	4.41	7.06	6.58	8.56	4.71	7.54
		$\phi_s = 0.80$	4.76	7.53	7.04	9.26	5.05	8.10
		$\phi_s = 0.85$	5.02	8.00	7.51	9.98	5.37	8.68
		$\phi_s = 0.90$	5.32	8.54	8.01	10.64	5.72	9.26
		$\phi_s = 0.95$	5.65	9.01	8.46	11.30	6.03	9.85
	$G_{n,2}$	$\phi_s = 0.75$	4.49	7.12	6.70	8.92	4.79	7.66
		$\phi_s = 0.80$	4.78	7.59	7.15	9.58	5.11	8.23
		$\phi_s = 0.85$	5.11	8.06	7.63	10.25	5.43	8.82
		$\phi_s = 0.90$	5.41	8.54	8.10	10.93	5.78	9.33
		$\phi_s = 0.95$	5.71	9.09	8.55	11.61	6.10	9.93
	$G_{n,3}$	$\phi_s = 0.75$	4.51	7.18	6.80	9.11	4.81	7.78
		$\phi_s = 0.80$	4.84	7.65	7.26	9.78	5.13	8.36
		$\phi_s = 0.85$	5.14	8.13	7.71	10.46	5.45	8.88
		$\phi_s = 0.90$	5.44	8.61	8.20	11.14	5.81	9.48
		$\phi_s = 0.95$	5.75	9.09	8.65	11.76	6.13	10.01

Table 6. Summary of system reliability indices β of stainless steel frames subjected to combined gravity and wind loads (average of three dead load cases GW1, GW2 and GW3).

Design framework	$\gamma_{M,s}$ or ϕ_s	Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4	Frame 5	Frame 6	Average
Eurocode framework	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.00$	2.58	2.49	2.33	2.24	2.55	2.59	2.46
	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.05$	2.72	2.63	2.48	2.39	2.69	2.74	2.61
	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15$	3.01	2.89	2.74	2.67	2.95	3.00	2.88
	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.25$	3.24	3.15	2.97	2.93	3.20	3.25	3.12
	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.55$	3.94	3.80	3.63	3.65	3.86	3.95	3.81
US framework	$\phi_s = 0.75$	3.78	3.81	3.45	3.52	3.52	3.55	3.60
	$\phi_s = 0.80$	3.59	3.62	3.26	3.30	3.32	3.34	3.40
	$\phi_s = 0.85$	3.41	3.44	3.08	3.11	3.14	3.15	3.22
	$\phi_s = 0.90$	3.23	3.27	2.91	2.93	2.97	2.98	3.05
	$\phi_s = 0.95$	3.07	3.11	2.76	2.76	2.82	2.82	2.89
Australian framework	$\phi_s = 0.75$	3.69	3.70	3.37	3.43	3.41	3.43	3.51
	$\phi_s = 0.80$	3.48	3.52	3.19	3.23	3.26	3.28	3.33
	$\phi_s = 0.85$	3.32	3.35	3.02	3.04	3.10	3.11	3.15
	$\phi_s = 0.90$	3.11	3.19	2.85	2.87	2.93	2.89	2.97
	$\phi_s = 0.95$	3.00	3.03	2.70	2.71	2.72	2.75	2.82

Table 7. System safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_s for stainless steel frames subjected to combined gravity and wind loads for different target reliability indices β_0 .

Design framework	Target reliability index	Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4	Frame 5	Frame 6	Average
Eurocode framework	$\beta_0 = 2.50$	0.97	0.95	1.03	1.07	0.96	0.95	0.99
	$\beta_0 = 2.75$	1.04	1.09	1.15	1.18	1.07	1.05	1.09
	$\beta_0 = 3.00$	1.14	1.18	1.26	1.28	1.16	1.15	1.20
	$\beta_0 = 3.80$	1.49	1.55	1.63	1.61	1.52	1.48	1.55
US framework	$\beta_0 = 2.50$	1.13	1.13	1.03	1.03	1.06	1.05	1.07
	$\beta_0 = 2.75$	1.05	1.06	0.94	0.94	0.97	0.97	0.99
	$\beta_0 = 3.00$	0.97	0.98	0.87	0.87	0.88	0.89	0.91
	$\beta_0 = 3.50$	0.82	0.83	0.74	0.75	0.75	0.76	0.78
Australian framework	$\beta_0 = 2.50$	1.19	1.12	1.00	1.01	1.00	1.03	1.06
	$\beta_0 = 2.75$	0.99	1.04	0.93	0.93	0.96	0.95	0.96
	$\beta_0 = 3.00$	0.94	0.96	0.85	0.86	0.89	0.90	0.90
	$\beta_0 = 3.50$	0.80	0.81	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.72	0.75

Table 8. Comparison between the required cross-section dimensions for the direct design and the *two-step* design approaches for different design frameworks.

Frame	Direct design approach	<i>Two-step</i> approach					
		Eurocode framework		US framework		Australian framework	
	Cross-section	Cross-section	Difference in area [%]	Cross-section	Difference in area [%]	Cross-section	Difference in area [%]
Frame 1	150×100×4	160×110×4.5	17.5	175×115×4.2	18.3	185×120×4.1	20.7
Frame 2	250×150×4	260×150×4.5	13.0	255×165×4.7	18.6	250×165×4.6	15.9
Frame 3	150×100×4	155×105×4.3	10.4	175×105×4.0	11.2	175×105×4.0	11.2
Frame 4	250×150×4	250×150×4.6	12.6	255×150×4.7	15.5	250×155×4.7	15.5
Frame 5	150×100×4	160×110×4.3	13.9	170×115×4.2	16.8	170×115×4.2	16.8
Frame 6	250×150×4	265×170×4.5	18.2	260×150×4.6	15.9	240×155×4.7	13.3
Average			14.3		16.1		15.6